

ISic2972

I.Sicily inscription 2972

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, Museo Iudica, inventory 2270

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI175473

1. Ἰοάνις
2. Ἰουστῖνος²⁶ Ἰωάννης | Ἰουστῖνος²⁶
3. διάκον-
4. ος.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 494016

EDCS 39300425

PHI 175473

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 14.0587

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1953. Palazzolo Acreide. Epigrafi cristiane nella collezione Iudica. *Notizie degli Scavi di Antichità*. 345-352. At 345 no.1

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2972. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387821>